

A CNN-BASED APPROACH FOR FACIAL EMOTION RECOGNITION USING HYBRID FEATURE FUSION

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Abstract

Facial Expression Recognition is a machine learning problem which aims to improve human computer interaction, pain estimation, healthcare monitoring and emotion detection. While many methods have been implemented for this problem, the overall performance is still unsatisfactory. In this work, a combination of Histogram of Gradients (HOG), Facial Landmarks, HOG features from a sliding window, and Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) features are used. HOG and Sliding Window HOG are used as handcrafted feature extraction techniques, while CNN is used as an automated feature extraction technique. At the end, handcrafted and automated features were concatenated in the fully connected layer of the CNN for emotion detection. The combination of handcrafted and automated features represents the latest evolution in image classification. A comparative analysis is conducted on FER2013 dataset for four different combinations of the above stated techniques. The comparative discussion of implementing these methods highlights that as the number of features extraction techniques increases, accuracy improves.

INTRODUCTION

Facial expression (FE) is used for understanding others perspective or point of view about a discussion or incident [1]. Facial expression (FE) [2] plays an important role in interpretation of behavioral emotions and

social interactions. Many handcrafted feature approaches such as Local Binary Pattern (LBP) [3], Histogram of Gradients (HOG) [4], Support Vector Machine (SVM) [5], Random Forest (RM) [6], and automated feature

generation approaches like Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) [7], Deep belief networks previously used for facial emotion estimation Studies have shown that fusion of handcrafted and automated features and assembling of automated features give better result about a particular problem. This study will focus on fusion of multi handcrafted and automated features for facial emotion estimation. Facial expression is used for non verbal communication and has lot of application like AI tutor system for feedback providing, psychological studies for pain

detection [8], Human behavior interpretation using robots, Mobile applications for emotion insertion, automated security etc. Issues have been risen by the researches in facial expression estimation like pose, illumination, low pixel density, baseline identification etc. Previously conventional approaches used for facial emotion estimation are: SVM, HOG etc [9, 10]. Recently automated approaches used for FEE like CNN [11]. Recently researches have shown that assembling of automated features and fusion of handcrafted and automated features CNN [12].

Fig. 1 Tarnowski, Kołodziej et al.

Recognition and differentiation of faces are innate human capacities, but computers are now performing these tasks. The capabilities of face detection and recognition enhance security, identify criminals, provide payment facility without card and provide other services. Face recognition is one of the most important and debated topics in research, with extensive studies aimed at enhancing security and applications in law enforcement and commercial settings, particularly in rising security needs [13, 14]. Many studies have identified critical issues in human computer interactions, particularly concerning human machine emotional communication.

Image classification is one of the popular research area in which machine learning and deep learning models [15] are employed to build robust applications that tackle complex real world scenarios. While traditional statistical models are also employed [16], deep learning techniques gain better performance. In human-computer interactions, the emotional connection between humans and machines has gained significant attention. Among humans, emotional expressions are the most powerful and natural way of communicating. However, facial expressions during spontaneous interactions often involve noticeable head movements, temporal variations, and partial occlusions, which complicate their

interpretation. Additionally, using facial expressions to accurately represent human emotional states is challenging, as these expressions are highly sensitive to factors such as lighting conditions and dynamic head movements [17]. It's challenging to categorize specific emotions because they are so diverse. People can mimic facial expressions that reflect distinct emotions in response to similar facial cues, which often occur in certain emotional situations. In terms of emotion recognition, past research has explored various machine learning and deep learning models to analyze and classify emotions.

A. Limitations

Fusion-based facial emotion estimation is nothing but the combination of multiple modalities or sources of information for improving the precision and robustness of facial emotion recognition systems [18, 19]. Fusion methods enhance emotion estimation performance but carry some limitations in themselves. Here are a few of the major limitations associated with fusion-based facial emotion estimation:

1) Availability and Compatibility of Multiple Modalities

Most of the fusion methods use different sources of data, like facial expressions, voice, physiological signals, or eye movements [20]. However, collecting and aligning these modalities is complicated, and the possible collection and utilization of all the modalities may not be easy to apply practically [21].

2) Increased Computational Complexity

Usually, fusion methods require much more complex algorithms and computational resources to combine and analyze data from different sources. This can pose significant

implications for processing times and resource usage, thus complicating its real-time implementation, especially on resource-constrained devices [22].

3) Sensitivity to Noise and Outliers

The existence of noisy or outlier data points in any one modality of multimodality fusion may degrade the performance of the result of fusion. Inaccurate or irrelevant information within one modality can significantly degrade the performance of the fusion results with loss of accuracy and reliability [23, 24].

4) Limited Generalization

Since the fusion-based approaches rely on very high-quality and representative training data, which must cover as good a cross-section of different scenarios as possible, if the training data are not diverse or biased toward particular populations, environments, or cultural contexts, the fusion model may not generalize as well to unseen or challenging situations [25].

5) Interpretability and Explainability

Fusion methods are usually sophisticated models and methods, which makes it difficult to understand the decision-making process. Understanding how and why certain modalities contribute to the final emotion estimation can be challenging, which may limit the trust and acceptance of fusion-based systems in certain domains [26, 27].

6) Privacy Concerns

Fusion methods may require collecting and integrating data from multiple sources, potentially including sensitive information such as physiological signals or voice recordings. Ensuring privacy and data protection becomes crucial when dealing with such data, requiring appropriate measures to be in place [28].

B. Objectives

The objectives of our study are follows:

1. Efficiency enhancement for facial emotion estimation using multiple fused features.
2. Proposed stated approach for different domain problems (like pain estimation, real-time activity recognition).
3. Reduction of high computational cost (in case of Handcrafted features generation approaches) and under fitting problems (in case of Automate Features generation approaches) using proposed fused features approach.

I. LITERATURE REVIEW

Traditional methods used for facial emotion estimation required lot of time and cost. So automated features generation approaches proposed for facial expression estimation. But automated feature generation approaches have limitations too like for large data sets AF approaches have data augmentation and over fitting problems [29, 30]. Data augmentation means if an object is placed at different orientations (in our case pose) then it is difficult for the system to recognize facial emotion. Moreover, for large data sets system learns extra features those are not required for a particular problem (Over fitting). So fusion techniques proposed which gave better results compared to HF and AF individually. In [31] before training the architecture image is fine tune (to overcome illumination problems) using local binary patterns for emotion estimation. Then RGB original image and LBP mapped code is used for different CNN architectures (VGG-S, VGG-2048, VGG-M-4096) individual training as well as ensemble architectures training (VGG-S-LBP 10 Cyclic, VGG-M-4096-LBP 1). Ensemble architectures results were good. Although margin was least [31].

In [32] handcrafted and learned features fusion is used for facial pain estimation. Histogram of gradients, geometric features and deep CNN features fused using SVR (support vector regression) for pain intensity estimation. For comparison RMSE (root mean square error) and CORR (Pearson Correlation) is used. Proposed method outperforms. 14% is increased in performance measure. 2% increase in CORR and 70% reduction in RMSE. Moreover, the problem remained the same as system performed well on frontal images, for side pose images performance was not good. In [33] handcrafted features fused with CNN features to recognize ear. Handcrafted approaches were used like LPQ (Local phase quantization feature), Local binary patterns, Histogram of gradients, BSIF (Binarized statistical image features), POEM (Pattern of oriented edge magnitude). For learned features CNN was used. Score fusion was used to fuse the learned and handcrafted features. All possible combination of handcrafted with handcrafted and handcrafted with learned features were used for fusion. Fusion of handcrafted features with CNN results were better. Normalization of handcrafted features results were better.

In [34] MRE-CNN (Multi region Ensemble - CNN) was proposed for better facial expression estimation. Alexnet and VGG-Net was used. Firstly, system detected face, then divided it into different parts like mouth, nose, ear etc. Then SoftMax was used as activation function. Proposed architecture results were better as compared to previously proposed solutions. In [35] audio (Handcrafted) and video features is used for emotion detection. Two types of fusion are used. Early fusion and late fusion. Different combination proposed like CNN + Transfer learning, CNN + Pre-Processing, SVM + Audio features proposed approach used pre-

train CNN features combined with handcrafted audio feature outperforms.

In [36] different CNN architectures are combined with handcrafted features using BOVW (Bag of Visual Words) to achieve high accuracy results for facial expression recognition [37]. Three CNN architectures VGG-13, VGG-f, VGG-Face used. VGG-13 trained from scratch only others were used pre trained. SIFT ~ KNN ~ SVM used for handcrafted features. Proposed architectures

outperformed by least margin as compared to recent proposed approaches [38]. In [39] multi stream CNN features fusion was used for driving behavior recognition. Abnormal driving can cause different swear accidents. To overcome this problem stated architecture was proposed. It gets input from different streams of CNN architecture. Fused the features using SVM (Support Vector Machine) late fusion.

For early fusion score-based approach is used as shown in fig 2.

Fig. 2 Hu, Lu et al. 2019

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Approach compared with different handcrafted features. Early fusion using score base results were better as compared to late fusion using SVM. In [40] MLVSF (Multi-layer visual feature fusion) approach was proposed. In medical image analysis handcrafted feature were performing well as compared to automated features. Proposed approach was used to fuse different handcrafted, mid-level and dense level features [41]. These features extracted by LBP, Bag of Visual Words and CNN (Alexnet, VGG Net) respectively. Experimental results showed that MLVSF can improve CNN for better accuracy. The suggested model of [2] creates emotion labels for every video sample by using video data as its input.

Using a face detection and selection procedure, we first identify the most important face areas based on the video data. We next use three CNN-based architectures to extract the facial picture sequence's high-level characteristics. In addition, we modified an extra module for every CNN-based architecture in order to record consecutive information for the whole video dataset. Using two publicly available datasets, AFEW 2016 and SAVEE, the integration of the three CNN-based models in a late-fusion-based strategy produces a competitive outcome if contrasted to the baseline technique. The Multi-feature Fusion Based Convolutional Neural Network (MFF-CNN), a compact network for image-based FER, is proposed in [1]. The suggested model extracts local characteristics from sixteen

patched images of the original picture using the Patch Branch and extracts both mid-level and high-level global features from the whole input image using the Image Branch.

In [42] author presented a unique multimodal approach based on deep learning to efficiently recognize facial emotions while veiled. The method recorded speech and facial emotions using two well-known datasets, CREMA-D and M-LFW-F. Then, utilizing fusion techniques, a multimodal neural network was constructed, which outperformed traditional unimodal approaches in face expression recognition. In order to identify the five distinct face emotions

(angry, pleased, neutral, sad, and startled), [43] early and late fusion approaches. These methods make use of various combinations from the publicly available VIRI databases, which contain visible, infrared, and multispectral dynamic imaging (MSX) photos, as well as the NVIE database. One unique aspect is the way that ResNet-18 and transfer learning (TL) are combined using concatenation and combining approaches to produce a model that is far more accurate than separate models. The summary of the literature review is presented in table 1.

TABLE 1: REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Sr. No.	Reference	Methodology	Visual Features	Data Set
1	Levi et al. [31]	LBP Map code and Original RGBImage is used to train different CNN (VGG-S, VGG-2048)	Fine tune image using LBP Extraction of Automated Features using CNN	CASIA Web Face Dataset
2	Edgede et al. [32]	Fusion of HoG and CNN using SVR	Extraction of Handcrafted features using HoG Extraction of Deep Features using CNN	Self-generated
3	Fan et al. [34]	Multi Region Ensemble CNN	Crop the Image into sub regions ensemble each sub region score using sum operation	RAF-DB (Real world affective faces Database)
4	Georgescu et al. [36]	Fusion of local, deep and handcrafted features	Handcrafted approaches (BOVW) Automated feature approach (CNN - VGG-F, VGG-Face) Fusion using SVM	FER
5	Liu et al. [40]	MLVSF (multi-layer visual feature fusion)	LBP was used for low level feature extraction. SIFT was used for mid-level feature extraction. For deep features extraction CNN was used. Features selection using SVM	Lymphoma DB, Histology DB

6	Ortega et al. [35]	Fusion of Audio (Handcrafted) and Video features	For audio features reocla was used. For video features CNN was used. Early fusion using Score base, Late fusion using SVR.	FER Dataset
7	Do et al. [2]	Horizontal fips, rotation left, rotation right, and Gaussian noise	Utilizing CNN-based networks to extract facial expressions' high-level characteristics	AFEW 2016 and SAVEE
8	Zou et al. [1]	Convolutional neural network	Fusion-based Convolutional Neural Network with Multiple Features (MFF-CNN)	CK+, JAFFE and Oulu-CASIA
9	Shahzad et al. [42]	Unimodal technique	Multimodal face recognition technique that combines a high-level self-learning feature with low-level facial key point characteristics	CREMA-D and M-LFW-F

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Dataset and Preprocessing

The FER2013 (Facial Emotion Recognition 2013) dataset consists of 35788 grayscale images, each representing one of seven distinct facial emotions with labels ranging from 0 to 6. During preprocessing, all the images were normalized to the range of 0, 1 to ensure consistent pixel scaling. Each image in the FER2013 dataset has a dimension of 48*48, which was used as the input size to train the model. The dataset is divided into three parts, 28,709 images for training, 3589 images for validation and 3589 images for testing. Table 2 provides the details of the number of images for each class in the FER 2013 dataset used in our work.

TABLE 2: FER 2013 DATASET

Classes	Validation and Testing	Training Data	Total Data
Angry	958	3995	4953
Disgust	111	436	547
Fear	1024	4097	5121
Happy	1774	7215	8989
Sad	1247	4830	6077
Surprise	831	3171	4002
Neutral	1233	3589	28709

B. Proposed Fusion features-based approach for emotion detection

In our study, we use Histogram of Gradients (HOG), facial landmarks, HOG features from sliding window for handcrafted feature extraction. Then, we extract the automated features using the CNN model. Finally, we fuse the multiple handcrafted features (Facial landmarks, HOG, HOG from sliding window) with automated features (CNN) using Score Base Approach/SVR. After that, we test the images for facial expression estimation using the fused features and classify the seven emotions of the face using the CNN model. Four distinct models are proposed, leveraging various combinations of features and fusion

techniques, including facial landmarks and different configurations of CNN and HOG features, ultimately improving the accuracy of emotion estimation Fully connected layers in the CNN architecture generate abstract feature vectors essential for emotion classification. Stochastic gradient descent (SGD) optimizes the CNN weights, employing a batch size of 128 over 20 epochs with dynamic learning rate adjustments. The model with the minimum validation loss is selected for classification, ensuring optimal performance. The training parameters for our CNN model are shown in Table 3, and the model diagram of our work is illustrated in Fig. 3

Fig. 3 Proposed Architecture

TABLE 3: TRAINING PARAMETER FOR OUR CNN MODEL

Parameter	Value
Batch Size	128
Epochs	20
Learning Rate	Dynamic Adjustment
Selection Criterion	Minimum Validation Loss

C. Models

We divided the methodology into four parts each uses a different model.

Model 1: CNN is used for feature extraction from RAW Data. The extracted features are then classified using the CNN.

Model 2: Facial Landmarks and Feature Extraction by CNN are utilized, which are then fused and classified by CNN.

Model 3: Facial Landmarks and Feature Extraction by CNN and HOG are utilized, which are then fused and classified by CNN.

Model 4: Facial Landmarks and Feature Extraction by CNN, HoG and Sliding Window Hog Features are utilized. These features are then fused together and classified using CNN.

III.RESULTS

A. First Experiment

In the first experiment, we used 1000 Images per label. With a total of 7 classes, we utilized a total of 7,000 images in our first experiment. Label Labels fewer than 1000 images used all available images. The testing accuracy for all the models are presented in table 4.

Fig 4 shows the result of the first experiment, in which we achieved an accuracy of 82.7% with 7,000 images.

TABLE 4: 1ST EXPERIMENT (1000 IMAGES PER LABEL ~ FER 2013)

Model	Description	Data Set	Accuracy
M1	CNN & RAW DATA	Testing Accuracy	75.5
M2	CNN, Facial Landmarks	Testing Accuracy	79
M3	Facial Landmarks and HoG	Testing Accuracy	79.5
M4	CNN, Facial Landmarks, HoG, and Sliding Widow	Testing Accuracy	82.7

Fig. 4 Results of the first experiment using 1000 images per label

B. Second Experiment

In the second experiment, we used 2000 Images per label. With a total of 7 classes, we utilized a total of 14,000 images in our second

experiment. Labels fewer than 2000 images used all available images. The testing accuracy for all the models in experiment 2 are presented in Table 5.

Fig 5 shows the result of the first experiment, with 14,000 images. in which we achieved an accuracy of 75.8%

TABLE 5: 2ND EXPERIMENT (IMAGES PER LABEL USED WAS 2000 ~ FER 2013)

Model	Description	Data Set	Accuracy
M1	CNN & RAW DATA	Testing Accuracy	72.5
M2	CNN, Facial Landmarks	Testing Accuracy	74
M3	CNN, Facial Landmarks & HoG	Testing Accuracy	74.2
M4	CNN, Facial Landmarks, HoG, Sliding Widow	Testing Accuracy	75.8

Fig. 5 Results of the second experiment using 2000 images per label

C. Third Experiment

In the third experiment we used the whole dataset. The testing accuracy for all the models in experiment 4 are presented in Table 6. Fig 6

shows the result of the third experiment, in which we achieved an accuracy of 68.5% with whole FER2013 dataset.

TABLE 6: 3RD EXPERIMENT (FER 2013 WHOLE DATA)

Model	Description	Data Set	Accuracy
M1	CNN & RAW DATA	Testing Accuracy	63
M2	CNN, Facial Landmarks	Testing Accuracy	65
M3	CNN, Facial Landmarks & HoG	Testing Accuracy	65.9

M4 CNN, Facial Landmarks, HoG, & Sliding Window Testing Accuracy 68.5

Fig. 6 Results of the 3rd experiment whole FER 2013 dataset

IV. DISCUSSION

In our study, we extract both handcrafted and automated features and then perform

classification on the FER2013 dataset using a CNN model. Our proposed model is compared to existing models, as shown in Table 7.

TABLE 7: COMPARISON OF THE PROPOSED WORK

Authors	Dataset	Model	Accuracy
Zahara, L. [44]	FER2013	CNN	65.97%
MC Gursesli [45]	FER2013	CLCM, MobilenetV2, ShuffleNetV2	63%, 58%, 65%
Sidhom, O. [46]	FER2013	-	66.1%
Yan, O.J. [47]	FER2013	CNN	63.97%
Proposed work	FER2013	CNN	68.5%

All these models use the same FER2013 dataset but differ in architecture. Among these, our proposed model outperforms the existing models in emotion detection tasks.

A. Sensitivity

The sensitivity, sometimes referred to as recall or true positive rate, concentrates on the ability to recognize genuine positives. It is calculated using equation (5.3):

$$\text{Sensitivity} = \frac{TP}{TP+FN} \quad (5.3)$$

V. PERFORMANCE MATRICES

The matrices used to evaluate the performance of this module are:

B. Accuracy

According to its definition, it is the proportion of accurate forecasts—both positive and negative—to all predictions. It is calculated using equation (5.4):

$$\text{Accuracy} = \frac{TP+TN}{TP+TN+FN+FP} \quad (5.4)$$

VI. CONCLUSION

Our study underscores the significance of the presented fusion-based techniques in enhancing facial emotion estimation. Comparative analysis against other fusion-based methods revealed notable improvements, particularly when dealing with limited datasets. Despite their simplicity, the proposed techniques exhibit robust performance and require only a single input image, making them practical for real-world applications. A thorough analysis of the mathematical model for estimating facial emotions provided additional insight into the fusion process, which breaks down the original image into three separate parts: the SVR feature, the HOG feature, and the facial landmarks. These components are seamlessly integrated to create a rich feature vector that enables better emotion estimation.

The study also gives four distinct processes/models to compare. It used handcrafted features from the FER 2013 dataset downloaded from Kaggle. The results of thorough testing and evaluation made it clear that, even when used on small datasets, the suggested models outperformed other models. In particular, the hybrid selection of learned features versus handcrafted features gives good performance while showing the benefit in incorporating different feature representations. Very briefly, this work has brought methodology towards advancing facial emotion estimation techniques by constructive solutions with promising performance. Continued

research in fusion methodologies and addition of multiple feature representations will further enable the system to learn even more precisely and robustly concerning affective recognition. This shall benefit all applications into which affective computing and human-computer interaction can be integrated.

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